

EDGE EFFECTS ON THE COMPRESSION DOMINATED FATIGUE RESISTANCE OF GRAPHITE-EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Laminates made with two graphite/epoxy systems, a first generation system and a second generation toughened system were tested under static and cyclic loading. Cyclic loading test results indicate that stacking sequence selection affects fatigue life of laminates more significantly than the material system selection. The MRLife6™ Code based on the critical element approach was used to predict the fatigue life of composite laminates under compression-tension cyclic loading.

Keywords: graphite/epoxy, fatigue, compression-tension, edge delamination, stacking sequence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Complex failure mechanisms may develop in multilayered, symmetric, angle-ply composite laminates, under uniform axial strain. Therefore, any analytical estimates that predict growth of defects and failure in laminates should be based on a stress-state analysis that can account for the anisotropic nature. In laminate composites, free edges (eg. the side of the laminate, holes or cutouts) give rise to interlaminar shear and normal stresses which are a function of the stacking sequence, the fiber orientation and the loading conditions. Thus narrow regions close to the free edges are very susceptible to delaminations which may accelerate the failure process. Under compressive cyclic loading, delamination is observed to be the most prevalent life-limiting mode of damage [1]. The presence of delamination leads to redistribution of stresses within the laminate and in general, to losses in stiffness, strength and fatigue life. The objective of this paper is to evaluate the fatigue life under compression-tension loading of two composite materials (IM6/5245C and AS4/3501-6) with two different stacking sequences. It is part of a research program investigating the mechanical behavior of graphite-epoxy laminates under static and cyclic loading and a continuation of previous studies on IM6/5245C composite material [2,3,4]. The MRLife6™ Code, developed by the Material Response Group of the Virginia Polytechnic Institute (MRG, VPI) [5], has been used to predict life of the laminates under cyclic loading. As mentioned by the authors [5], the delamination model within MRLife6™ is not fully calibrated. The delamination failure model in MRLife6™ is still under development and this development has been recently stimulated through a collaboration between the Institute for Aerospace Research (IAR) and MRG, VPI. Experimental results reported in this paper have shown some limitations of MRLife6™ and improvements to the software are suggested.

2. FREE-EDGE STRESS ANALYSIS

Studies on graphite-epoxy laminates including 0° , 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ angle plies have shown that failure mechanisms may be predicted from stress states at free edges. A quasi-3D finite element program, developed by Lahoud [6], was used to account for the different lamina orientations and to define the stress distributions within seventeen laminates under a uniaxial tensile or compression strain of $\pm 1\%$.

The lay-up for all laminates was $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]$ (44%/44%/11%) 18-ply symmetric. In this paper, the results are reported for two laminates with the following stacking sequences:

Laminate 2: $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ]$

Laminate 12: $[90^\circ/0^\circ/+45^\circ/0^\circ/+45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ]$

These stacking sequences were selected because under compression loading, interlaminar normal stresses of opposite signs were calculated at the free edge. The stress values computed at $2t$ (t : ply thickness) from the free edge, were chosen as representative of the state of stresses at the free edges, as suggested by Sun and Zhou [7]. The distance $2t$ was equal to 0.28 mm, in the case of these laminae. This approach led to predictions of static strength of laminates in tension and in compression which correlated well with experimental values [2]. A detailed stress analysis for both laminates can be found in [4].

This analysis showed that for compressive loading of laminate 12, the largest positive normal

stresses σ_z as well as the largest shear stresses τ_{xz} occurred at the $45^\circ/0^\circ$ (5th/6th ply) and at the $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ (6th/7th ply) interfaces. Normal stresses σ_z are also important in the 7th to 9th interfaces. On the basis of these calculations delamination in a mixed mode would be expected within the 5th or the 6th interface ($45^\circ/0^\circ$ or $0^\circ/-45^\circ$), or delamination in Mode I, under compressive loading, at the 9th interface ($-45^\circ/-45^\circ$). In laminate 2, the compression dominated load ratio ($R=-3.75$) constant amplitude loading used resulted in negative normal stresses σ_z between $0^\circ/90^\circ$ plies and high shear stresses in $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ interfaces. Thus the $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ (1st/2nd ply) and the $-45^\circ/+45^\circ$ (8th and 9th ply) interfaces were expected to delaminate first in our cyclic tests.

Figure 1. Test specimen supported with anti-buckling guides held in hydraulic grips.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

The specimens used in this investigation were prepared and tested in the Structures and Materials Laboratory of the IAR. Large panels (61 cm x 30.5 cm) of IM6/5245C and AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composites were fabricated with stacking sequences 2 and 12. The 2.5 mm thick panels were cut into specimens 290 mm long x 25.4 mm wide. Prior to testing, the specimens were inspected using an ultrasonic

C-scan and were found to be free of detectable flaws. The specimens were tested using an MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine under stroke control for static tests and load control for cyclic loading tests. The load was transferred to the specimens through a hydraulic gripping system which maintained a constant pressure of about 34 MPa over a 60 mm length at each extremity. The gripping areas of both the specimen and the jaws were lightly sand-blasted to prevent slippage during loading. Aluminum anti-buckling guides (12.6 mm wide x 152.4 mm long) supported the central portion of the specimens tested in compression (Figure 1). A thin Teflon sheet was inserted between the specimen and the anti-buckling guide to minimize the friction.

Tension-compression fatigue tests were conducted under load control using a sinusoidal wave form, with a load ratio $R = P_{min}/P_{max} = -3.75$ and a frequency of 5 Hz. The P_{min} load varied from a low of $0.6P_{uc}$ (P_{uc} - static strength in compression) to a high of $0.9P_{uc}$. The P_{uc} load for each laminate was determined from a number of static tests. The values for IM6/5245C were -43.5 kN and -35.9 kN for laminates 2 and 12 and for AS4/3501-6, -48.5 kN and -41.6 kN for laminates 2 and 12 respectively. The number of cycles to failure recorded corresponds to the final fracture of the specimen (complete loss of load carrying capability).

A traveling microscope was used to observe the development of edge damage during the cyclic tests. In addition, three inspection techniques were employed: celluloid film replication of the edge [8], ultrasonic C-scan (Portascan pulsed echo scanner), and photoelastic coatings (PC-1 coating, reflection polariscope model 031 manufactured by Micromeritics Group). Replicas were taken from the edge of specimen at different numbers of fatigue cycles. The first replica was taken after the delamination was just detected by the microscope or photoelastic coating. Very thin (0.25 mm) photoelastic coatings, when observed through a compensator, are sensitive to local changes in the stiffness of the specimen. These changes are due to an accumulation of microcracks and delaminations. This simple and inexpensive technique allows damage growth to be monitored in situ as opposed to C-scan inspection which requires removal of the specimen from the test machine. The periodic ultrasonic C-scan inspection was used to verify photoelastic technique indications of delamination initiation and propagation.

4. FATIGUE RESULTS

Results of fatigue tests are presented on Figure 2 in terms of the normalized applied load level

Figure 2. Fatigue test results. Average of 3 to 5 tests are plotted.

Comparison of life prediction and tests results for AS4/3501-6

Figure 3. AS4/3501-6 laminates. Average test results with standard deviation (scatter) compared to MRLife6 predictions.

Comparison of life prediction and tests results for IM6/5245C

Figure 4. IM6/5245C laminates. Average test results with standard deviation (scatter) compared to MRLife6 predictions.

$S = P_{min}/P_{uc}$ versus the number of cycles to failure. The data points on the plot represent the average of 3 to 5 tests per load level. The data scatter is shown in Figures 3 and 4 and is consistent with normal fatigue behaviour of composites. The average life to failure is plotted along with ± 1 standard deviation. When comparing the fatigue lives for different materials and stacking sequences the differences in P_{uc} must be considered.

Figure 5. IM6/5245C laminate 2 specimen with photoelastic coating. Center of the specimen is obscured by anti-buckling guides. Specimen failed after 797,794 cycles so the images represent 0.09, 0.56, 0.94 and 0.999 life time (LT). The white area in the lower left corner of the specimen seen at 0.56, 0.94 and 0.999 LT indicates delamination.

The results clearly show that at the same applied load level S:

- the fatigue life of laminates 12 is ten to one hundred times lower than that of laminates 2;
- the fatigue behavior of laminate 12 for both IM6/5245C and AS4/3501-6 are similar while the IM6/5245C laminate 2 is more resistant to fatigue than AS4/3501-6 laminate 2.

5. OBSERVATION OF FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION

Though the testing programme is not yet completed some conclusions can be reached from the experimental observations, especially for laminate 2. First, the edge stress analysis as well as the Azimuth

code supplied with MRLife6TM correctly pointed to the interfaces which delaminated. The microscopic and replica observations were consistent. The photoelastic coatings showed [2] that under tensile loading, the delamination appeared as a strip along the free edge of the specimen in accordance with O'Brien's model [9,10]. In compression, the fatigue delaminations were localized, following an initiation period several small delaminations appeared along the free edge of the specimen (Figure 5). Usually one of these delaminations would grow toward the laminate interior and would eventually lead to final failure of the specimen. The final failure was preceded by visible buckling of the delamination.

6. MRLife6TM LIFE AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH PREDICTION CODE

The MRLife6TM Code [5] is based on a mechanistic modeling approach including the evolution of properties of composites under cyclic loading. It requires a precise definition of damage accumulation mechanisms and failure modes. The method is based on the choice of a representative element divided into a critical element and subcritical elements. The critical element controls the final failure event, while subcritical elements participate in the internal stress redistribution, defined by local geometry changes such as stiffness reduction. In the delamination case the critical element is chosen as the undelaminated ligament that finally buckles or crushes. The propagation rate (da) is controlled by a Paris Law in the form:

$$\frac{da}{dn} = A(G)^B \quad (1)$$

where A, B are empirical parameters and G is the strain energy release rate. The approximate expression from O'Brien [9,10] is used to calculate the strain energy release rate:

$$G = \frac{\epsilon^2 t}{2} (E_{Lam} - E^*) \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the applied laminate strain, t is the laminate thickness, E_{Lam} is the elastic modulus of the undelaminated composite, and E^* is the elastic modulus of the completely delaminated composite. The fatigue life prediction greatly depends on the damage propagation rate. The MRLife6TM Code does not consider the respective influence of modes I, II and III on the delamination growth rate (equation (1)) and assumes that the delamination is a strip along both free edges of the specimen (O'Brien's model).

7. FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION

In MRLife6TM only the post initiation behaviour is modeled. On the basis of experimental free-edge observations using photoelastic coatings the initiation period was found approximately equal to half of the specimen life. Though these observations require further experimental substantiation, the half life ratio for the initiation phase was used in the present study. The need for another model to predict the initiation phase in the fatigue life appears as one of the limitations of MRLife6TM.

The representative element in the specimen life calculations was chosen to have a length equal to twice the width of the delamination ($\frac{a}{2}$) which allowed the observed delamination to be approximated with O'Brien's model. The specimen was presumed to have reached the end of its life when the undelaminated fraction of the laminate width could no longer support the load. The A and B parameters were calculated from the short duration fatigue data (obtained at higher load levels). Since these parameters for a given material system depend on the particular combination of failure modes (I,II and III) within the interface, a method for calculating these from basic fracture test data remains to be

developed. This may be viewed as an other limitation of MRLife6™ for the delamination failure mode case. However, the short term fatigue test may in fact be simpler to carry out than several basic fracture tests (Double Cantilever Beam, End Notch Flexure and Mode III test).

The results of MRLife6™ calculations, multiplied by two to take into account the initiation phase as mentioned before, are shown in Figures 3 and 4 (for AS4/3501-6 and IM6/5245C respectively) along with the experimental data. The calculated lives generally fell well within the scatter for the experimental data. This is largely due to the way in which the *A* and *B* parameters were calculated. It should be noted that at the load of $S=0.6$ for AS4/3501-6 laminate 2 and IM6/5245C laminate 12, MRLife6™ significantly underestimates the life of the specimens. The cause of this discrepancy warrants further study both experimentally and analytically at lower loads. It is expected that the failure mode for these lower load cases is different than assumed which would have led to the breakdown of the delamination model.

8. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The compression dominated fatigue tests performed for this study as well as the analytical work done on the finite element stresses analysis and the life prediction with MRLife6™ lead to the following conclusions and remarks:

- Stacking sequence selection can affect the fatigue life of composite specimens by up to a factor of 100 in both brittle and toughened graphite/epoxy systems.
- Where the fatigue failure process occurs through delamination associated with high interlaminar shear stresses the toughened epoxy system IM6/5245C appears to be superior to the AS4/3501-6.
- More experimental observations at lower load levels (i.e. $S=0.6$) are needed.
- The MRLife6™ requires extensive experimental experience before an adequate critical element selection can be made.
- Improvements in the delamination model are needed for MRLife6™.
- Better understanding and analytical models of delamination initiation are needed.
- The MRLife6™ provided an excellent tool for focusing and directing experimental and analytical efforts.

9. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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10. REFERENCES

1. Dupont, L., "Etude du comportement mécanique d'un composite stratifié graphite/epoxy soumis à des sollicitations monotones et cycliques" NAE Contractor Report NAE-CR-2 (1989) NRC .

2. Lefebvre, D., Komorowski, J.P., Roy, C., Masmoudi, R., "Free-Edge Influence on the Static Strength of Graphite/Epoxy Laminate", Proc. of CANCOM91, "Composite Structures and Materials", eds: Hoa, S., Gauvin, R., Elsevier Applied Science, 1992, pp.470-477.
3. Komorowski, J.P., Heath, J.B.R., Lefebvre, D., Roy, C., Masmoudi, R., "Influence of Edge Effect on Compression-Tension Fatigue of Toughened Graphite/Epoxy Laminates", Proc. of AGARD 73rd SMP workshop: Utilization of Advanced Composite Materials in Military Aircraft, San Diego, Cal., 6-7 October 1991, publ. by Structures and Materials Panel, AGARD, NATO, AGARD-R-785, April 1992, 7:1-7.
4. Lefebvre, D., Masmoudi R. and Roy, C., "Comportement des stratifiés carbone-epoxy IM6/5245C sous charges de tension-compression statique et cyclique", IRA Contractor Report, IAR-CR-16 (1992) NRC.
5. Reifsnider, K.L., "MRLifeTM - Simulation of Performance and Life Prediction for Composite Laminates, User's Manual", Materials Response Group, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Oct., 1991.
6. Lahoud, A.E., "AEE: A Finite Element Program for the Analysis of Edge Effects in Composites, Research Dept. # AEL-11-86, U. Sherbrooke Civil Eng. Dept (1986).
7. Sun, C.T. and Zhou, S.G. "Failure of Quasi-Isotropic Composite Laminates with Free Edges" J. of Reinf. Plast. and Compos., p. 515 (1988).
8. Pendelton, R.L., Tuttle, M.E., Editors, "Manual on Experimental Methods for Mechanical Testing of Composites", Society for Experimental Mechanics, 1989.
9. O'Brien, T.K., "Characterization of Delamination Onset in a Composite Laminate", Damage in composite Materials, ASTM-STP 775, Reifsnider, K.L., Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1982, pp. 140-167
10. O'Brien, T.K., "Analysis of Local Delaminations and Their Influence on Composite Laminate Behavior", Delamination and Debonding of Materials, ASTM-STP 876, W.S. Johnson, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1985, pp. 282-297